

ISic3130

I.Sicily inscription 3130

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

limestone

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Agrigentum

Place of origin (modern)

Agrigento

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Boston, USA, Boston Museum of Fine Arts, inventory 1972.391

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR136231

1. Ἄλκιμος ἔγλυψε

Edition: PHI330185

1. Ἄλκιμος

2. ἔγλυψε.

3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645471

EDR 136231

EDCS 64800549

PHI 330185

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 28.0761

Comstock, M.B., Vermeule, C.C. 1976. Sculpture in stone: the Greek, Roman and Etruscan collections of the Museum of Fine Arts, Boston. Boston. At 57 no.89 ph

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3130. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4388171>